

MEDICAL DENT TOOTHPASTE ANALYSIS OF ORAL CAVITY PROPHYLAXIS, HYGIENE AND AGAINST DISEASE

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Abstract: The composition and technology of the medical dent toothpaste for oral cavity prevention, hygiene and combating diseases, which contains mavrak, chamomile, fieldberry, blackcurrant fruit and other types of products, during the production of the paste with medicinal substances and other chemicals proportionality was seen. The product has been shown to be effective during use by consumers of all ages and to minimize the growth of oral bacteria.

Key words: Tooth, prevention, hygiene, caries, stomatitis, inflammation, infection, biologically active additives (BAA).

The aim of the article: For patients with dental problems, prevention and treatment of primary stomatitis, prevention of diseases of the oral cavity, strengthening of teeth and gums, treatment of vitamin deficiency disease (singing) in teeth and gums, control of oral bacteria. minimize the increase.

Introduction: Around the world, several oral health measures have been implemented. The most popular method is to use a toothpaste. However, chewing sticks are still used in many cultures around the world in a conventional manner. Chewing sticks have a mechanical cleansing action similar to a toothbrush in addition to their antimicrobial effect. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the effect of Miswak on the growth of Candida species and to compare it to that of toothpaste. A cross-sectional study was carried out on some selected randomly volunteers from January to April, 2023. Two groups of participants were used for

two weeks. The participants were separated into a group used Miswak and a group use ordinary toothpaste. Samples were collected before and after two weeks in these two groups. Samples were immediately processed for microbiological phenotypic conventional methods and in vitro susceptibility testing of the microbial isolates to antimicrobial. The findings show that a significant effect of Miswak against an oral cavity candida species.

Prevention (Greek. prophylaktos safety) is a set of measures aimed at preventing the origin and spread of diseases, protecting and strengthening health. Prevention of dental diseases is the prevention of the occurrence and development of diseases of the oral cavity. This direction is considered a priority in modern dentistry, and the experience of many countries shows that the simple quantitative growth of the dental staff, financing and material provision of dental services, changing the current situation in the prevalence and intensity of dental caries and periodontal diseases will not be enough for. The use of reliable preventive programs of the world dental practice leads to a sharp decrease in the intensity of tooth caries and the intensity of periodontal diseases, it plays an important role in reducing the cases of early tooth loss in children and in reducing the number of children and adolescents with artificial teeth. The reliable evidence is that the cost of preventive methods is on average 2 times lower than the cost of treating dental diseases. It is not logical to continue to spend significant material resources on treating diseases that can be prevented with preventive measures at a simple and low cost. Therefore, the prevention of dental diseases should include the introduction of a system of social and individual comprehensive preventive measures aimed at creating conditions that eliminate risk factors for dental diseases. If the conditions affecting the development of the diseases are not changed in a certain direction, if the conditions that affect the development of the diseases are not changed in a certain direction, it is necessary to wait for their further increase. In order to prevent dental diseases, especially among children, it is appropriate to direct the tourism of the whole society [1-3].

Toothbrush and toothpaste are an integral part of oral hygiene. Its effectiveness mainly depends on the teeth and teeth cleaning methods. Every consumer should be convinced that careful and correct care of the oral cavity is the most important preventive and auxiliary therapeutic treatment. A dentist's role includes teaching patients the necessary practices to maintain good oral hygiene to prevent dental caries and periodontal disease.

Good oral hygiene maintenance is a key to prevent oral diseases. Miswak is used in the Arab world and represented by flexible and strong sticks. This study conducted for the first time in Libya to investigate the anti-candida activities. The findings showed that Miswak displays certain antifungal activity compared to toothpaste particularly against *C. albicans*, *C. dubliniensis* and *C. glabrata* strains.

The highest candida count in colony forming units was recorded in toothpaste group indicating the least antifungal activity while the least candida count was recorded in Miswak indicating the highest antifungal activity. A significant difference between Miswak before and after using while there no significant difference between the toothpaste group before and after using. Several studies assessed Miswak and its effect on oral health. Miswak was containing several medicinal properties and scientifically was proved to be helpful even when used alone and without other methods of cleaning teeth. It has also been indicated that Miswak released a variety of beneficial chemicals such as fluoride, saponins and sterol which possess antimicrobial activity. Chewing minimizes Miswak contamination. Miswak Chewing stick stimulates salivary flow. Saliva plays a vital role in maintaining homeostasis by balancing the pH in the oral cavity. As a result, using Miswak can reduce the risk of oral microbial contamination and translocation. The antimicrobial activity of released phytochemicals reduces the number of candida. Studies have indicated that Miswak possesses antifungal properties compared to ordinary toothpaste, thus, preventing oral candidiasis [35, 36]. Where the Naeini et al. [37] reported from an in vitro study that alcoholic extract of Miswak have strong to moderate activity, on oral Candida species, including *C. albicans*, *C. dubliniensis* and *C. glabrata*. More, hexane components in

roots of Miswak were found robust against *C. albicans* [37]. In current study, an assay after two weeks was conducted to illustrate the difference between Miswak use and toothbrushes with toothpaste. Where the results showed that Miswak affected candida in all the investigated strains. Miswak was much more effective than toothpaste in eliminating candida immediately and after two weeks of use. These results indicate that the extracts of Miswak contain compounds with a therapeutic potential against different *Candida* strains, and hence, they can potentially be utilized as therapeutic agents. The significance of this study came from an *in vivo* assessment of Miswak on oral candida that was followed up on for two weeks. In case of both treatments are combined or used, Miswak has antibacterial and antifungal activities as well as preventing plaque. Toothpaste contains fluoride which prevents tooth decay and thus, the use of both for one month may reach an ideal level of oral hygiene and dental health. On the other hand, more studies are needed to verify the use of Miswak as an effective mean to improve oral hygiene tools and fungicidal therapeutically agent for *C. albicans*. Conclusion: Miswak reduces substantially the total oral fungus more than toothpaste, thus, Miswak use can limit the risk of oral candida species contamination and translocation.

The result: The objects of the research (BAA) are additives obtained from medicinal plants on the basis of Biologically Active Additives. Traumatic inflammation of the mucous membrane of the oral cavity has a very diverse appearance: from catarrhal inflammation to ulcerative or hyperplastic manifestations. The cause of injury can be external traumatic factors, local defects and deformations of teeth. Also, careless dental practice or restless behavior of the patient can be an etiological effect. Young children require special attention, it is very difficult to diagnose and treat diseases of the mucous membrane of the oral cavity. Knowing the clinical manifestations of traumatic injuries of the mucous membrane allows choosing the optimal medical tactics in each clinical case. Based on the review of literature, liquid extracts from medicinal plants serve to increase the strength of teeth and minimize the growth of oral cavity bacteria.

Conclusion: The composition and technology of the paste containing Mavrak, chamomile, dalchoi, blackcurrant and other types of products will be determined during the production of the paste with medicinal substances and other chemicals. According to the obtained results, our product has shown results such as that consumers from 7 years to 70 years of age give their results during the period of use and minimize the growth of oral cavity bacteria. Pastes enriched with medical products and vitamins, unlike other types of toothpaste, are distinguished by the fact that they do not have side effects, are easily applied to the teeth, and are effective in the treatment of gums. In the future, various researches are being conducted in order to further enrich the composition of toothpastes and increase the efficiency coefficient.

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